

**RESTRICTED STUDENT YOUNG PEOPLE THROUGH PHYSICAL
CULTURE AND SPORTS TRAINING**

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Anatisation: In this article, this article provides clear information about the education of students with disabilities through physical culture and sports, how they needed to bring them up in spirit of patriotism through physical education.

Key words. Individual restrictions on disabled, disabled, Daan syndrome, epilepsy, adolescents, inclusive, inclusive.

In the last few decades, the organizations that provide limited adolescents have developed a human rights approach based on the problem of disability, based on human rights-based approach and explanation. Both approaches are based on the social model of disability. Here it is a problem for human rights and changes that can be actively involved in the life of society. These models emphasize the opinion that the people with disabilities will weaken the structure of society not to the public process of public life. On this basis, the capabilities with limited access to the most people are uniting to fight for their rights.

Since many years of scholars have been continuing to comment and interpret the concept of disability in the world. It seems that the appearances of all conflicts are serious about how people describe disability in this regard. Such a look is rich in debate, which is of this or in this or this policy and living in developing countries as a common explanation for the formation of disabilities with disabilities as a common explanation.

The skill that all members of human birth were born enough in terms of conditions that the full member of the society was preserved. As a result of a newborn child, the child arises and disability is reflected in his physiological view or, as a result of dumb changes, causing a constant understanding of disability. A permanent concept of disability is not something "in place" with human health. Such a view is equal to the physical violation of disabilities. The blindness, the dormancy of physical disabilities shall apply to the blindness, the dangerous cases, psychic diseases, as well as Daun syndrome and epilepticity.

Such a medical look often calls disability to physical disability to physical disability. In general, persons with disabilities are socially accepted, people with disabilities are socially and they are anymore, unusual among all other medicative interventions, and or subject to rehabilitation interventions. They

understand like obvates. Someone may be recognized when someone has to work with people with disabilities, when they are considering physical constraints, in this paradigm, as a result of a restriction resulting in disability april viewed. As such as this is expressed in this case, the problem is expressed as pure medical medicine, then it is mainly decided by treatment and rehabilitation; Reorhere requires justice in special institutional organizations. This is done to ensure caring and protection of such a work with disabilities, as in cases of special professionals in cases of institutionalism or to restore regulatory operation.

A child with the functional disorders feels that all other children need to have to communicate with people kindness and intimacy. No difficulty or other human situation should be in a hurry to make far-away decisions that parents cannot comprehend or practice practice. We know that the kindness of parents plays an important role in intellectual and movement functions, as well as emotion and personal development of children. That is why the doctors and other organizations of the doctors required these ethical standards and this psychology with great attention to this psychology.

If a child with disabilities cannot live with his parents and is not familiar to his parents, then the child must place a child in the senior group of non-group living homes.

The exchange of employees must be minimal. Because this is how it can ensure that the child will defeat the full protection of the child and communicate with people who substitute a parent.

The child with a lifestyle has the need for a unique growth and development in an environment that enriches knowledge and skills that enrich its emotional impressions. In children, these necessary needs in children cannot be met in large institutions that form a misdemeanor of employees against children. In such institutions, the practice, not only to specific children, but was often unique. In this case, a servant will be responsible for maintaining several children, in recent cases, in recent cases, is considered to be children's needs not by the current turnover.

Group homelands of housing - stupidity, dormitories, not only necessary physical care. First of all, he must have his own houses for children, and the third is the third way to open the way to these children to the children's children and developing programs. A disability with disabilocated child should prevent the child not only to make new impressions, but not only healing, physical education, but also for technique that strengthens his actions.

If a child has a flaw in view, it should make a certain actions aimed at creating confidence. They teach the child to start and understand the skills of movement and to start to understand those around them. If we come to a child with hearing, we need to teach them the time of mammal time. In the first year of the child is done using a separate gesture later using special gestures. In general, persons with disabilities are one of the responsibilities of the social worker that urges to live a normal life by evaluating the positions of social life.

The solvency of adolescents in the upbringing of adolescents is one of the current issues of today. But today, too many teenagers are excluded from education for various reasons. Consideration of organizational, scientific-methodical measures for inclusive education should be developed to develop measures related to training and retraining of specialists.

There are two main factors in attracting adolescents in general education institutions:

First, children with a special need can also act together with healthy children. When it is organized in accordance with inclusive education, special needs will be protected by special needs, and healthy children feel more kind and careful about children with disabilities.

Second, children with disabilities have the right to read, upbringing side by side with healthy peers.

The success of this work should be reflected in the laws of each state. Because laws guarantee them the provision of necessary material and spiritual resources. In teaching children with disabilities, parents, neighborhoods are required to work in cooperation with teachers, specialists, and is obligatory.

Children with special needs can also be studied and developed with healthy peers, study, education, vocational studies, education, vocational. The purpose of inclusive education, children in need of assistance are being protected from their social and their equal rights in social life, they can learn to learn with their peers. The existing defects in the segregation and specialized types of children, whose segregation and indoor or indoor containers are much higher, but as a result of a narrow circle of children in the school team, they face great difficulties in the future. Special schools have very great shortcomings in these aspects. In addition, the living of special needs from the general public not also in terms of democracy. Because the children of special needs have rights as well. The analysis shows that about 10-15% of about 10-15% need special education.

The need for attracting special children to general education institutions occurs that the place of living with special needs completely exposed to special needs,

or the place of material money is very far The lack of lack of parents or parents' avoidance of their own child to a special institution is to prevent socialism, solving the issue of equality, discrimination.

The issue of inclusive education has become a center of attention in the 90s. Final work papers were studied on integrated training programs in South Africa and Southeast Asia. As a result, the Ministries of All States were adopted in the educational Ministries as an alternative to the special departments under special schools.

The need for inclusive education stems from its existence to society and children with special needs:

Inclusive education always allows children to be in the circle of their family mahalla and relatives.

Placing children from their families, flee from home, their family will be blocking the right to participate in the life of the community. From his family, a child from his family, far from his parents, will grow hard. Because the family is the head of upbringing.

Inclusive education can serve as a catalyst, which leads to improving the quality of education. The admission of special needs to general education institutions encourages students to develop new teaching methods that are more active and more students. The nafs of this touches everyone.

There is a very misconception relative to the society. There may be such a lack of information about the lack of information and closed training in specialized institutions from young ones. It is a considerable work to lose or reduce such an attitude. But from the experiment, it is well known that children understand differently and similarity aspects. If the special needs have been educated with children in the normal development, it would have ensured that all children are not to realize that they were as themselves as themselves as they disabled people.

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